

ANIKO KOVAČ
SAARLAND UNIVERSITY
ANIKOK@COLI.UNI-SAARLAND.DE

MAJA MARKOVIĆ
UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD
MAJAMARKOVIC@FF.UNS.AC.RS

A Rule-Based Syllabifier for Serbian

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WHAT DID WE SET OUT TO DO?

The Goal

- i) Develop a system for automatic rule-based syllabification for Serbian
- ii) Provide an analysis of the outcomes to address theoretical considerations and serve as a basis for the development of future syllabifiers
- iii) Present syllable distribution data for Serbian

WHY RULE-BASED?

Our Approach

- Rule-based vs. data-driven
- Existing rule descriptions:
 - Gramatika srpskoga jezika* by Stanojčić and Popović (2005)
 - + Kašić (2014)
 - + Zec (2000)

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

- (1) In words made up of multiple phonemes, consonants, sonorants and vowels, the syllable boundary comes **after the vowel and before the consonant**.

či-ta-ti [to read]

- (2) ~~Medially, in a consonant cluster which has an affricate or fricative sound in its initial position, the syllable boundary will be before that consonant cluster.~~

po-šta [post]

- (3) ~~The syllable boundary will be before a consonant cluster if, in a consonant cluster found medially in a word, the second position in the cluster is occupied by one of the sonorants v, j, r, l or lj preceded by any other consonant besides a sonorant.~~

sve-tlost [light]

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

- (1) In words made up of multiple phonemes, consonants, sonorants and vowels, the syllable boundary comes **after the vowel and before the consonant**.

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- (2) ~~Medially, in a consonant cluster which has an affricate or fricative sound in its initial position, the syllable boundary will be before that consonant cluster.~~

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- (3) ~~The syllable boundary will be before a consonant cluster if, in a consonant cluster found medially in a word, the second position in the cluster is occupied by one of the sonorants v, j, r, l or lj preceded by any other consonant besides a sonorant.~~

sve-tlost [light]

tr-ča-ti [to run]

r-va-ti se [to wrestle]

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

- (1) In words made up of multiple phonemes, consonants, sonorants and vowels, the syllable boundary comes **after the vowel or sonorants r, l and n in syllable bearing positions** and before the consonant.

či-ta-ti [to read]

- (2) Medially, in a consonant cluster which has an affricate or fricative sound in its initial position, the syllable boundary will be before that consonant cluster.

po-šta [post]

- (3) The syllable boundary will be before a consonant cluster if, in a consonant cluster found medially in a word, the second position in the cluster is occupied by one of the sonorants v, j, r, l or lj preceded by any other consonant besides a sonorant.

sve-tlost [light]

tr-ča-ti [to run]
r-va-ti se [to wrestle]

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

- (4) If a consonant cluster consists of **two sonorants**, the syllable boundary will be **between them** so that one sonorant belongs to the preceding, and one sonorant belongs to the following syllable.

lom-ljen [broken]

- (5) If a consonant cluster consists of a **plosive** in its initial position and **some other consonant except the sonorants j, v, l, lj and r**, the syllable boundary will be **between** the consonants.

lep-tir [butterfly]

- (6) If in a cluster of two sonorants, the **second position is occupied by the sonorant j from je** corresponding to the **ijekavica dialect** to e in the ekavica dialect, the syllable boundary will be **before that group**.

čo-vjek [man]

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

- (4) If a consonant cluster consists of **two sonorants**, the syllable boundary will be **between them** so that one sonorant belongs to the preceding, and one sonorant belongs to the following syllable.

lom-ljen [broken]

- (5) If a consonant cluster consists of a **plosive** in its initial position and **some other consonant except the sonorants j, v, l, lj and r**, the syllable boundary will be **between** the consonants.

lep-tir [butterfly]

- (6) If in a cluster of two sonorants, the **second position is occupied by the sonorant j from je** corresponding to the **ijekavica dialect** to e in the ekavica dialect, the syllable boundary will be **before that group**.

čo-vjek [man]

gu-ngula [commotion]
mo-mci [boys]

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

- (4) If a consonant cluster consists of **two sonorants**, the syllable boundary will be **between them** so that one sonorant belongs to the preceding, and one sonorant belongs to the following syllable.

lom-ljen [broken]

- (5) If a consonant cluster consists of a **plosive or nasal** in its initial position and **some other consonant except the sonorants j, v, l, lj and r**, the syllable boundary will be **between** the consonants.

lep-tir [butterfly]

- (6) If in a cluster of two sonorants, the **second position is occupied by the sonorant j from je** corresponding to the **ijekavica dialect** to e in the ekavica dialect, the syllable boundary will be **before that group**.

čo-vjek [man]

gu-ngula [commotion]
mo-mci [boys]

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

(7) The sonorant r can be a syllable carrier in standard Serbian when:

a. it is found medially between two consonants,

tr-ča-ti [to run]

b. it is found initially before a consonant,

r-va-ti se [to wrestle]

c. it is found after a vowel in compounds,

za-r-đa-ti [to rust]

d. before o that is realized as an I in other members of the paradigm.

o-tr-o (m.) from o-tr-la (f.) [wiped]

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

(7) The sonorant r can be a syllable carrier in standard Serbian when:

a. it is found medially between two consonants,

tr-ča-ti [to run]

b. it is found initially before a consonant,

r-va-ti se [to wrestle]

c. it is found after a vowel in compounds,

za-r-đa-ti [to rust]

d. before o that is realized as an l in other members of the paradigm.

o-tr-o (m.) from o-tr-la (f.) [wiped]

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

(7) The sonorant *r* can be a syllable carrier in standard Serbian when:

a. it is found medially between two consonants,

tr-ča-ti [to run]

b. it is found initially before a consonant,

r-va-ti se [to wrestle]

except if it is followed by the sequence *je*.

c. ~~it is found after a vowel in compounds,~~

~~*za-r-đa-ti* [to rust]~~

d. ~~before *o* that is realized as an *l* in other members of the paradigm.~~

~~*o-tr-o* (m.) from *o-tr-la* (f.) [wiped]~~

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

(8) The other two alveolar sonorants, l and n can be syllable carriers in:

a. dialectal toponyms,

Stlp, Vlča glava, Žlne

b. foreign toponyms,

Vltava, Plzen

c. personal names, and in

English *Idn* or Arabic *Ibn-Saud*

d. the word

bicikl [bicycle].

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

(8) The other two alveolar sonorants, l and n can be syllable carriers in:

a. dialectal toponyms,

Stlp, Vlča glava, Žlne

b. foreign toponyms,

Vltava, Plzen

c. personal names, and in

English *Idn* or Arabic *Ibn-Saud*

???

d. the word

bicikl [bicycle].

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

- (8) The other two alveolar sonorants, l and n, can be syllable carriers if they are found medially **between two consonants of lower sonority, initially before a consonant of lower sonority, or finally after a consonant of lower sonority.**

*Stlp, Vlča glava, Žlne,
Vltava, Plzen*

English *Idn* or Arabic *Ibn-Saud*
bicikl [bicycle]

HOW DID WE SEGMENT?

The Rules

- (8) The other two alveolar sonorants, l and n, can be syllable carriers if they are found medially **between two consonants of lower sonority, initially before a consonant of lower sonority, or finally after a consonant of lower sonority.**

*Stlp, Vlča glava, Žlne,
Vltava, Plzen*
English *ldn* or Arabic *lbn-Saud*
bicikl [bicycle]

Bern not Be-rn
Klajn not Kla-jn
Linkoln not Linko-ln

HOW ABOUT THE DATA?

The Results

- 3,607,450 word-forms in *SrpLemKor* (Popović, 2010; Utvić, 2011)
- Most frequent syllable types:
CV (62%), CCV (12%), V (11%), and CVC (9%)
- Positional distribution data for different syllable types in monosyllabic words for the initial, medial, and final positions of polysyllabic words
- Asymmetries of syllable structures occurring only in monosyllabic words and the final position of polysyllabic words:
CVCC, CCVCC, VCC, CVCCC, CCCVCC, VCCC, CCVCCC, CCCC VCC, and CCCVCCC
- Syllable nuclei statistics including their overall and positional frequencies in monosyllabic and polysyllabic words

HOW ABOUT THE DATA?

The Results

- ~2% noise in the data
- 6 syllable structures not found by an onset-maximization syllabifier in Croatian (Meštrović et al., 2015)

CCCCVC *mo-na-rhstvom*

CCCCV *se-rbska, ca-rstva*

CCCCVC *de-jstvom*

CCCCCV *se-rbstvo*

CCCCVCC *Go-Idštajn, Rot-hchild, Ar-mstrong*

CVCCCC *cr-no-gorskg*

CLOSING THOUGHTS

Conclusions

- We developed a rule-based syllabifier for Serbian based on prescriptive rule descriptions.
- In the process, we discovered the shortcomings and inaccuracies of the existing prescriptive rule set.
- This approach still has some issues that should be resolved.
- A combination of onset maximization following (Meštrović et al., 2015) and the rule descriptions might provide an accurate capture of native speaker intuition.

THE END

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- Draga Zec. 2000. O strukturi sloga u srpskom jeziku. *Južnoslovenski filolog*, 56(1-2):435–448.

